

TechConnect
Human Tech Index

HUMAN-TECH SKILL COMPLEMENTARITY CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK DEVELOPMENT

Deliverable 1.1

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<p>Abstract</p>	<p>The Human-Tech Skill Complementarity Conceptual Framework provides findings from desk research on relevant concepts exploring the relationships between human and technologies. This report proposes a new concept of 'Human-Tech Skill complementarity', which systematically explores the collaboration mechanism between human and technology skills in a two-way interaction. A comprehensive concept of Human-Tech Skill Complementarity is provided, addressing the intricate relationships between human skills and technology.</p>
<p>Keywords</p>	<p>Human-Tech Skill complementarity; complementarity theory; paradox theory, both/and thinking, impacts</p>

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Nature of deliverable:		
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* *R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)*

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patent filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

DATA: Data sets, microdata, etc

DMP: Data management plan

ETHICS: Deliverables related to ethics issues.

SECURITY: Deliverables related to security issues

OTHER: Software, technical diagram, algorithms, models, etc.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

TechConnect thoroughly explores the ongoing debate regarding the influence of emerging technologies on human labour and skills. It places a distinct emphasis on Human-Tech Skill Complementarity, highlighting the essential interdependence and mutual enhancement of both human and technological skills in a systemic manner. The primary goal is to deepen our understanding of the dynamic interplays between new digital technologies and human skills, generating novel and practical knowledge on this emerging topic of Human-Tech Skill Complementarity. The project brings together a multidisciplinary team and employs diverse methods, including policy analysis, systematic literature review, annual cross-sectoral industry landscape surveys, in-depth case studies in the healthcare sector and validating the findings beyond this sector via stakeholder engagement, workshops, and guidelines production. The key outcomes include the development and validation of the Human-Tech Skill Complementarity Conceptual Framework, Assessment Index, Strengthening Model, and TechConnect Stakeholder Toolkit. These outcomes reveal how new technologies such as AI and robotics affect human skills, emphasising the development and deployment of technologies that enhance individual skills and workforce capabilities. Adopting a collaborative approach, TechConnect forms a consortium with academics, industry partners, and a stakeholder engagement firm. This collaborative effort fosters partnerships with technology associations, professional groups, and government entities. Grounded in the research-informed, evidence-based and practice-driven approaches, TechConnect will make a meaningful impact on the quality of employment and competitiveness, contributing to social and economic resilience. The collective efforts of the consortium are geared towards disseminating findings and recommendations widely, with the ultimate goal of influencing policy and practice for inclusive growth in the digital landscape. This project will run over three years from October 2024 to September 2027.

As part of the TechConnect project, the goal of Work Package 1 (Conceptual framework development and landscape analysis, which runs for the main duration of the project, M1-M29) is to provide a conceptual, theoretical and empirical foundation for other WPs. WP1 includes literature review on Human-Tech Skill Complementarity; the development of a comprehensive conceptual framework on Human-Tech Skill Complementarity; and production of three annual landscape reports on Human-Tech Skill Complementarity, i.e. the continuous industry landscape analysis. The results will be fed into WP2, WP3 and WP4.

As part of **Work Package 1: Conceptual Framework Development and Landscape Analysis**, this document introduces **Deliverable D1.1: The Human-Tech Skill Complementarity Conceptual Framework**. Developed through extensive desk research on relevant theories and concepts, this deliverable explores the dynamic interplay between human and technological skills.

This report defines the novel concept of **'Human-Tech Skill Complementarity'** and systematically examines the mechanisms underpinning the two-way interaction between human capabilities and technological advancements. It offers a comprehensive framework that captures the intricate

relationships between human and technological skills, providing a foundation for fostering sustainable and impactful human-technology collaboration in organizational and societal contexts. The **Human-Tech Skill Complementarity Framework** clearly addresses the complexities of human-technology interactions. It serves as the theoretical cornerstone of the project, forming the basis for practical applications in **Work Packages 2 and 3 (WP2 and WP3)**, including case studies and sectoral analysis.

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ABBREVIATIONS

AI	Artificial intelligence
CTF	Communications Task Force
DoA	Description of Action
H	Human
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
T	Technology
WP	Work Package

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ABOUT TECHCONNECT

TechConnect, a €3 million initiative funded by the European Union, under the Horizon Europe framework with a consortium of 9 partners, Trinity College Dublin (TCD), Mälardalen University (MDU), Technical University of Madrid (UPM), Universiteit Utrecht (UU), BluSpecs, Tallaght University Hospital (TUH), Västerås Hospital (RV), Hospital Ramon y Cajal (FIBIRYCIS) and University Medical Center Utrecht (UMCU).

The TechConnect project aims to deepen the understanding of how advanced digital technologies impact human skills by focusing on Human-Tech Skill Complementarity. Through desk research, industry surveys, and case studies in healthcare, TechConnect explores how human skills and technology interact in real-world contexts. The project develops a systemic framework to address the gap between intended and actual technology use, offering practical guidelines for technology procurement, development, and training. By providing tools to enhance human-tech integration, TechConnect ambition is to boost productivity and employment across industries, driving greater alignment between technology and human skills.

1 Introduction

The rapid adoption of advanced digital technologies, such as artificial intelligence (AI) and automation is reshaping workplaces and decision-making processes across industries. Addressing a critical challenge, the **TechConnect** project focuses on enabling efficient and innovative collaboration between humans and digital technologies through **skill complementarity** and **co-evolution**.

Recent developments on advanced technologies such as AI, emphasize the interplay between human skills and emerging technologies, highlighting their mutual influence. However, existing research often portrays humans as users of static technologies, overlooking the dynamic, co-creative, and adaptive relationships that define modern human-technology interactions. As humans integrate technologies into work processes, their skills evolve, driving new modes of learning and adaptation. In turn, human inputs shape technological advancements, enhancing technologies' functional capabilities. This bidirectional interaction underscores the need for a comprehensive framework to understand how human and technological capabilities can co-evolve and complement one another.

To bridge this gap, this deliverable introduces the concept of **Human-Tech Skill Complementarity**—a novel and holistic framework that explores the synergistic, iterative relationship between human and technological skills. This framework moves beyond traditional paradigms to address how technologies can enhance, rather than displace, human skills, fostering meaningful collaboration and advancing both organizational and societal outcomes.

As part of **WP1**, this deliverable aims to conceptualize **Human-Tech Skill Complementarity** by integrating multidisciplinary insights from computing science, information management, and management, and psychology. The framework will:

- **Enhance Theoretical Understanding:** Provide researchers with a foundation to develop new theories on human-technology interaction.
- **Support Organizational Practice:** Help organizations understand the interplay between people, technologies, and systems to drive innovation and productivity.
- **Guide Policy Development:** Assist policymakers and social partners in designing strategies that promote decent work, employment quality, and productivity.

By advancing this framework, the project aligns with the broader goal of leveraging new technologies to complement human skills, create employment opportunities, and ensure decent working conditions, ultimately driving sustainable and inclusive growth.

2 Methodology

To explore existing concepts related to human-technology interactions, this study adopted a systematic and iterative approach to literature review. The research process began with an initial search and review of articles on the topic using primary search techniques and cross-referencing methods. The research team conducted preliminary reading and discussions to identify key themes and ideas emerging from the literature. From these discussions, a preliminary list of keywords was generated to refine the search process. Specifically, the search query used was: TS = (human OR employee) AND TS = (machine OR "AI" OR "Artificial Intelligence" OR robot OR "bots" OR computer* OR chatbot* OR algorithm* OR technology* OR autom* OR "intelligent automation" OR "smart device" OR intelligent* OR "automated service interaction") AND TS = (collaboration OR interface OR communication OR interaction) OR TS = Complementarity.** Cross-referencing method was used to further searches to broaden the scope of relevant articles. The search was executed on the Web of Science and Scopus database, chosen for its broad multidisciplinary coverage and high-quality research content. The retrieved articles represented diverse disciplines, encompassing literature relevant to the study's focus on human-technology collaboration and complementarity. The final step involved a rigorous screening process based on predetermined inclusion and exclusion criteria to ensure the relevance and quality of the selected literature. This systematic approach ensured the review captured comprehensive, high-quality insights from the existing body of knowledge, facilitating a robust theoretical and practical understanding of the topic.

3 Review Findings

Table 1 summarizes the definitions of key concepts related to the human-technology relationship. Based on the review, several notable findings emerge, including the multidisciplinary nature of the research, the inconsistency of concepts, and the predominant focus on spatial collaboration between humans and technologies.

3.1 Inconsistency in Concepts

Research on human-technology collaboration spans multiple disciplines, including management, information systems, and computing science, but inconsistent terminologies have been used. Concepts such as **human-AI collaboration** (Fügenger et al., 2022), **employee-AI collaboration** (Kong et al., 2023), and **human-algorithm interaction** (Donahue et al., 2022) highlight the varied approaches to understanding these relationships. Recent studies emphasize **human-technology complementarity**, such as **human-AI complementarity** (Inkpen et al., 2023), focusing on how humans and technology mutually enhance each other. This marks a shift from viewing technology as a static tool to seeing it as a dynamic, intelligent agent capable of transforming human skills and workflows (Chowdhury et al., 2022).

Traditionally, these studies have focused on **spatial collaboration**, where humans and technologies interact in shared environments. Robots and AI systems assist in repetitive or dangerous tasks, while humans focus on strategic thinking and creativity (Sowa et al., 2021). However, with digitalization, this collaboration is evolving into **virtual environments**, blending human creativity and critical thinking with AI's data processing capabilities (Kolbjørnsrud, 2024).

3.2 Static Relationships

While valuable, the predominant focus on **static relationships** in human-technology collaboration overlooks their dynamic and co-evolutionary nature. Existing research often emphasizes task division and coexistence in physical spaces (Raisch & Krakowski, 2021). Yet, with the rise of advanced technologies like AI, robotics, and machine learning, collaboration is shifting toward **co-evolution** and **mutual complementarity**, where humans and technologies continuously adapt and enhance each other's capabilities.

Over time, research has evolved from "technology usage" and "coexistence" to **collaboration** and **complementarity** (Tang et al., 2022; Li et al., 2023). However, much of the work remains static, focusing on fixed strengths—e.g., humans' strategic thinking versus technologies' computational power—without addressing mutual learning and adaptation (Donahue et al., 2022). This gap calls for a more dynamic framework that captures how humans and technology can co-learn and evolve to achieve innovative outcomes.

Table 1. Summary of related concepts

Concepts	Definitions	Key features	Focus	Reference	Disciplines
Human-algorithm collaboration	"a scenario where the combined system of human and algorithm achieves a lower average loss (or higher accuracy) than either the unaided human or the algorithm alone. This definition emphasizes the synergistic effect between human and algorithm, where their combined performance exceeds the capabilities of each individual component."	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Leveraging distinct strengths Team performance between H and AI 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Synergistic performance 	Donahue et al. (2022)	Computing Science
Human-AI complementarity	"the goal of achieving team performance in human-AI collaboration that surpasses the capabilities of either humans or AI working independently."	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Leveraging distinct strengths Team performance between H and AI 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Superior team performance 	Inkpen et al. (2023)	Computing Science
Human-AI interaction	"the process of interacting with human users through AI systems (e.g. virtual assistants or chatbots) in service scenarios"	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Interactive nature 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> User interaction 	Hui et al. (2023)	Information Management (IM)
AI-employee collaboration	"the collaboration between AI and employees in a working environment, where AI is viewed as a new collaborator (or new employee) working together with employees to optimize efficiency, flexibility, and creativity, thereby enhancing both employee and corporate productivity."	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tech as a new employee 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Efficiency and creativity enhancement 	Chowdhury et al. (2022)	Management
Human-AI collaboration	"the process of human interaction when collaborating with a system to complete a task"	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Interactive nature Tasks 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dynamic task allocation 	Fügener et al. (2022)	Management
Human-machine collaboration	"the partnership between humans and intelligent machines, with intelligent machines performing the mundane and repetitive tasks, allowing individuals to handle the more complex tasks."	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Partnership between H and T Different tasks for H and T 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Task complementarity 	Li et al. (2023)	Management
Usage of intelligent machines (i.e., AI, robots, and algorithm)	Employees use intelligent machines (i.e., artificial intelligence, robots, and algorithm) in their work.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Using technologies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tech users 	Tang et al. (2022)	Management

3.3 Skills

Existing research on skills often frames automation in a simplistic binary way. One pole of this binary is when automation is described in terms of substitution and refers to the possibility of the technology to replace humans by offering capabilities through which humans are made redundant in performing a particular task that previously required a particular human skill/set/. The other pole of the binary involves enhancement, i.e. the possibility of the technology to support the work of humans by offering capabilities that complements the skill/set/ that the human needs to perform a particular task. For instance, intelligent machines are seen as taking over mundane tasks, allowing humans to focus on more complex activities (Li et al., 2023). While this perspective highlights automation's impact on the labor market, it neglects the **dynamic interplay** between human and technological skills.

A more comprehensive approach is needed—one that explores how human skills (e.g., critical thinking, creativity, and emotional intelligence) and technological abilities (e.g., data processing and pattern recognition) complement and co-evolve. This perspective emphasizes the potential for humans and technologies to jointly enhance their respective capabilities, fostering greater innovation and efficiency.

3.4 Moving Forward

To address these gaps, future research must adopt a **dynamic and holistic perspective** on human-technology collaboration. This includes recognizing the evolving, co-adaptive relationships between humans and technologies, expanding beyond static models to explore how these partnerships drive mutual learning, skill development, and transformative outcomes. This approach will provide a richer understanding for researchers, practitioners, and policymakers alike, enabling the design of systems and strategies that fully harness the potential of human-technology collaboration.

4 Defining Human-Tech Skill Complementarity

As revealed in the concept review, while significant progress has been made in understanding human-technology relationships, existing concepts often oversimplify the complex interactions that occur when humans and technologies work together. These approaches frequently neglect the co-evolutionary and synergistic possibilities of human and technological skills, focusing instead on models of substitution or enhancement. Such perspectives fail to account for the broader potential of collaboration and joint development enabled by advanced technologies, such as artificial intelligence (AI) and robotics.

In this study, we build on prior research and draw on complementarity theory (Carson, 1969; Heider, 1982; Kiesler, 1983), paradox theory (Schad, Lewis, Raisch, & Smith, 2016; Smith & Lewis, 2011), and both/and thinking (Lewis & Smith, 2014; Smith & Lewis, 2022), we define Human-Tech Skill Complementarity as: *“A dynamic, multi-level synergy between human skills and technology capabilities, in which both reinforce and support each other across task, role, team, and organizational contexts, enhancing task performance and organizational efficiency. This complementarity depends not only on the functional attributes of the technology and the alignment of human skills but also on environmental factors, organizational support, and user behaviors related to active/passive technology usage.”* Such definition addresses the complex interactions that occur when humans and technologies work together as well as includes the co-evolutionary and synergistic possibilities of human skills and technology capabilities.

Humans have different skills and technologies have distinct functional capabilities. While technologies—such as AI and robotics—excel in evidence-based tasks, including data analysis, modelling, and rule-based operations, humans contribute cognitive and emotional skills, such as contextual understanding, empathy, and creativity. Rather than being static or competing, these skill sets function as two sides of the same coin, creating tensions which need to be harnessed productively. Complementarity theory has been applied into the human-technology interaction and proposed a balanced view. The origin of complementarity theory can be traced back to the conceptual framework proposed by Carson (1969). This theory was initially considered primarily applicable in relatively unstructured environments where interaction partners have equal status. The central premise of complementarity theory is that individuals often seek balance and compatibility between their attributes and those of their collaborators (Carson, 1969).

The interaction between human skills and technological skills may create tension, which often manifests as contradictions or dilemmas. The paradox theory provides an important theoretical perspective, emphasizing that these seemingly contradictory tensions can be reconciled and transformed into driving forces for high performance under appropriate management (Schad et al., 2016; Smith & Lewis, 2011). For example, in the simultaneous application of scientific rigor (provided by technology) and situational understanding (provided by humans), the combination of these different skills can create synergies. And 'both/and thinking' further provides a framework for this process, redefining the direction of this dialogue by emphasizing fusion and creative solutions, rather than simply viewing challenges as binary oppositions (such as technology versus humans) (Lewis & Smith, 2014; Smith & Lewis, 2022).

These theories play a crucial role in the conceptual framework of Human-Tech Skill complementarity. Drawing on the definition and above analysis, we visualise the Human-Tech Skill Complementarity framework in Figure 1. This framework explores the interaction between humans and technology in their respective but interrelated skills, advancing our understanding of how humans and technology work together. In order to better grasp this synergy, it is necessary to consider the specific context of their interaction. This interaction occurs in specific application environments, such as healthcare, manufacturing, and education, where humans and technology collaborate in different ways. In these contexts, technology is not just an auxiliary tool, but an active participant in decision-making, task execution, and innovation processes. Different types of technologies, such as artificial intelligence, robots, and data analysis tools, exhibit unique interactive patterns in their respective application scenarios, which in turn affect the complementarity of human and technological skills. Understanding the interactive relationships in these contexts helps us gain a deeper understanding of how humans and technology evolve and complement each other, thereby enhancing performance and promoting innovation.

Figure 1. A Conceptual Framework of Human-Tech Skill Complementarity

5 Assessing Human-Tech Skill Complementarity

Prior research indicates that the way humans engage with technology is shaped by both the features and materiality of the technology itself, as well as the skills possessed by individuals. However, current investigations into the effects of new, advanced digital technology on human labor often lack substantial empirical evidence, highlighting a need for more robust research in this area. In addition, existing studies fall short in providing adequate measurements for assessing Human-Tech Skill Complementarity, emphasising the necessity for comprehensive evaluation metrics.

With the main goal of advancing our understanding of the complementarity between humans and emerging technologies, such as AI/robotics, this project avoids oversimplification of the human-machine relationship in the existing research. Instead, we recognise and address the intricate nature of this relationship within its specific context. In our assessment of Human-Tech Skill Complementarity, we employ 'affordances': a concept derived from ecological psychology. This approach enables us to comprehend how human skills evolve, adapt, and synergise with technological skills.

Coined by ecological psychologists in the 1970s (Gibson, 1977), affordances refer to the potential actions an object offers. The concept recognises that a technology's use is not solely determined by its material properties; it evolves through user interaction, shaping the interplay of human skills.

In the TechConnect project, we explore both actual and imagined affordances of technologies, highlighting their dynamic interplay. This approach differs significantly from traditional perspectives that isolate the examination of specific technologies and human skills.

In terms of analysis, this project adopts a holistic system of thinking (Oliveira & Martins, 2011), by investigating the individual (task, role), team, and organisational level factors. This expanded scope transcends mere task assessment, aiming for a systematic evaluation of Human-Tech Skill Complementarity and its influencing factors, as illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Conceptualisation of Affordances Analysed at Different Levels

- The *first* level of analysis, i.e., the task level, will initially be described through ethnographic studies of the combinations of a specific technology-user. The focus is to capture how the technology-in-use affords a particular **task**. An example could be to map

how the use of an AI-supported imaging technology by a radiologist affords the task of *identifying causes for a medical condition* by the visualisation of, for example, a tumour.

- The **second** level of analysis is how technology-in-use affords the **work** of a person with a particular role and a particular occupation. Here, the analytical focus is on how, for example, AI-supported imaging technology, together with other technologies-in-use, becomes part of the *diagnosing work* of the radiologist.
- The **third** level of analysis is how the technology-in-use affords the **knowing** of particular occupations and teams. “Knowing” here refers to skills, competences and professional knowledge. On this level of analysis, the analytical focus is on how technologies-in-use, such as AI-supported imaging technology, becomes integrated into the joint practices of the group of radiologists, or the team of different healthcare specialists, who together work with a patient upon whom the AI-supported imaging technology has been used.
- The **fourth** level of analysis is how technologies-in-use together affords particular informal and formal **organisational structures** on department, unit or organisational levels, for example relationships and flows of information. On this level, the AI-supported imaging technology-in-use may, together with other technologies-in-use, afford particular power dynamics, certain organisational routines, etc.
- Finally, the **fifth** level of analysis is how technologies-in-use afford the vision/mission of the organisation; here, specifically, hospitals in this project. On this aggregated level, technologies-in-use could, for example, afford, people-centred care, data-driven care, or financially centred care, depending on the affordances of the technologies-in-use.

Embedding affordance in a systematic framework, as a novel approach, will produce insights by mapping affordance gaps between the actual and intended affordances, leading to the development of the Human-Tech Skill Complementarity Index. Derived from in-depth observational case studies within the 4 hospital partners, comprehensive data will be gathered through various methods such as observations, shadowing, photographing, interviews, focus groups, and document analysis. The resulting Index empowers organisations to assess and enhance their Human-Tech Skill Complementarity.

6 Conclusion

This deliverable introduces the **Human-Tech Skill Complementarity Framework**, a novel and holistic conceptualization that addresses the dynamic interplay between human and technological skills in modern workplaces. By integrating insights from computing science, information management, and human resource management, along with cross-sectoral survey data from diverse industries, the framework provides a comprehensive foundation for understanding how humans and technologies can co-evolve and complement one another.

The framework is designed to support researchers, practitioners, and policymakers in achieving three key goals:

- **Theoretical Advancement:** Offering a robust foundation for developing new theories on human-technology interaction.
- **Practical Application:** Equipping organizations with tools to optimize the integration of human and technological capabilities, driving innovation and productivity.
- **Policy Development:** Informing strategies that promote decent work, enhance employment quality, and support inclusive economic growth.

As the theoretical foundation of the **TechConnect** project, this framework will be applied in **WP2 and WP3** to analyze real-world case studies and sectoral practices. It reflects the project's commitment to enabling technologies to enhance, rather than displace, human skills, fostering innovative, equitable, and sustainable outcomes across industries.

By addressing the critical challenge of skill complementarity and co-evolution, this framework positions human-technology collaboration as a driver of meaningful employment and organizational success, ensuring both technological and human potential are fully realized in the digital age.

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